

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 18 (2025)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

| 2

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2025,
vol. 18

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

FINANCIAL ACCOUNTABILITY IN UDI AND EZEAGU LOCAL GOVERNMENT BUREAUCRACIES

Ugwueze Charles Afamuefuna ¹

Abstract

The specific objectives of this research were to: ascertain if internal financial control measures are properly adhered to in the two local governments; determine if external auditing is playing its strategic role effectively in the financial control of the two local governments; ascertain whether there are adequate authorization and recordings to provide reasonable accounting controls over revenue and expenditure in the two local governments; and ascertain the relationship between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial control in the two local governments. Descriptive survey research was adopted in interrogating the aforementioned objectives. The population of the study is 1200 employees from Finance, works, education, administration, health and agriculture departments of the two local governments under study. In order to get a representation of the whole population the Taro Yamani formular for sample size determination was used. It found that internal control measures are not properly adhered to in the two local governments; external auditing is not effectively playing its strategic role in the financial control of the two local governments; Udi and Ezeagu local governments do not maintain authorization and recordings to provide reasonable accounting controls over revenue and expenditure; and there is no effective system of checks and balances between the local government legislature and executive for financial control in the two local governments. The results imply that the local government functionaries in Udi and Ezeagu local government do not adhere to the principles of financial accountability in the conduct of the affairs of the council.

¹ Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria, Mobile Number: +2348034652176 Email: afamcharlesu@yahoo.com

Keywords: Financial Accountability, Local Government, Bureaucracy.

Introduction

The main thrust of public administration is to effectively manage public bureaucracies in a manner that includes the management of man, material, and money (Chioke, 2016). Local government as a bureaucracy plays a pivotal role in local governance (Ogunnubi, 2022). However, it is vivid that Nigerian local governments are facing several ugly ordeals (Chioke, Umeokafor & Mbamalu, 2020), which includes financial accountability. Arguably, Nigeria has both in the past and present had responsible and irresponsible leadership bedeviled by accountability challenges of different sort (Chioke, 2023). Unfortunately, it appears that there abound traces of this in Udi and Ezeagu local government bureaucracies. In recent times, there has been substantial agreement among some critics that the greatest problem of local governments today is not inefficiency, but lack of financial accountability. According to Laxmikanth (2001) accountability connotes the concepts of administrators to give a satisfactory account of their performance and manner in which they have exercised power conferred on them.

Financial accountability is enforced by means various controls. In other words, it involves devising various control mechanisms to keep the administration under a close watch and in check. Internal control consists of all measures employed by an organization to safeguard resources from waste, fraud and in inefficient utilization and to promote accuracy, and reliability in the accounting records. It also measures compliance with organisation's policy as well as evaluates the efficiency of operation (Meig, 1982; Coe & Sellis, 1991; Committee of Sponsoring Organisation, 1992). The control measure is just as relevant to local government as it is to profit making organizations. Inadequate control mechanisms can adversely affects the management responsibilities of local government's officials and place them in positions where they may be tempted to engage in questionable activities and accounting practices. It could subject individuals to unwarranted accusations of such activities (Duncan, Flesher & Stocks, 1999).

Research Background

Accountability is a central issue in public administration. Accountability is a role or behaviour, expectation or requirements of a lower person or authority towards another higher person or authority to have attained a certain predetermined standard. Sometimes, this expectation or requirement may involve a negative attainment, that is, the requirement or obligation, not to have done or yielded to certain behaviours. Whether it is positive or negative expectation, there is usually a set of rules or roles attached. But adherence to the rules by employees is the problem of managing organization. The problem is further compounded by the evolution of large organizations.

There is therefore, the need for an effective control system. Effective control measure is an indispensable tool in the hand of management that wishes to protect organization resources and control successive operations which lead to enhancing financial accountability. The degree of compliance with compliance with the control procedures is often affected by the negligence of duty, carelessness, mistakes and even personal factors. These factors are problems to the organization and eventually undermine the efficiency and effectiveness of the control mechanisms.

The problem of not having effective financial control measures has resulted to a situation whereby money meant for the development of the local governments ends up in a private pockets. Cases of embezzlement, mismanagement, misappropriation of fund abound in the local governments. Local governments are now facing tremendous financial problems to the extent that some of them cannot pay salaries any more. This underscores the need for proper financial accountability in our local government bureaucracies so that they can perform their primary responsibilities.

Lack of financial accountability in local government in Nigeria affects the overall performance of the councils. There is no remarkable improvement in the lives of the people at the grassroots level to show the existence of the local governments. According to Agbo (2010), the lack of integrity, transparency and accountability at the level of governance definitely constitutes a heavy toll on the well-being of ordinary Nigerians. Stealing has become a major hobby for local government officials. The monthly revenues accruing to the local governments are siphoned by the local officials without any positive impact on the general well-being of the people. Nobody accounts for local government money. Every day we hear reports of reckless spending of the local government resources by the officials of the

councils. It is this particular lack of financial accountability in local government in Nigeria that is responsible for the recent agitation for abolition of local governments in Nigeria.

The broad objective of this study is to interrogate financial accountability in Udi and Ezeagu local Government bureaucracies while the specific objectives are to: ascertain if internal financial control measures are properly adhered to in the two local governments; determine if external auditing is playing its strategic role effectively in the financial control of the two local governments; ascertain whether there are adequate authorization and recordings to provide reasonable accounting controls over revenue and expenditure in the two local governments; and ascertain the relationship between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial control in the two local governments. To attain the above research objectives, the research was guided by the following research questions: Are internal control measures properly adhered to in Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments? Does external auditing play its role effectively in the financial control of the two local governments? Are there adequate authorization and recordings to provide reasonable accounting controls over revenue and expenditure in the two local governments? Do effective checks and balances exist between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial control in the two local governments?

Bureaucracy, Financial Accountability and Local Government: A Brief Review of Literature

Bureaucracy is one of the commonest concepts in social science parlance but it is difficult to define as it does not mean one thing to everyone (Onwuka, 2008). Bureaucracy is the basic form for public sector in any society (Chioke, 2012). Hornby (2010) defined it as the system of official rules and ways of doing things that a government or an organization has, especially when these seem to be too complicated. Hence; bureaucracy is also change driven, because new policies and complicated rules are being given birth to everyday (Chioke, 2017).

Bureaucracy represents the hierarchical arrangement of authorities in the political and administrative terrains of any polity (Chioke, 2016). Ugwu and Okonkwo (2015) were of the view that, "Bureaucratization offers above all the optimum possibility for carrying through the principle of specializing administrative functions according to purely objective considerations. Individual performances are allocated to functionaries who have specialized training and who by constant

practice learn more and more.” At this juncture this research examines financial accountability.

Financial accountability system requires the government or officials to use public fund judiciously and responsibly render accounts of how public funds were used. It also entails that appropriate fiscal records are kept. Therefore, the financial accountability system is characterized by the establishment of pattern of control over receipts and expenditures that permit determination either by the executive or by the legislature or both, ensuring that public monies have been used for a public purpose (Abdulsalami, 1998). Periodic auditing of accounts, the provision of financial memoranda, etcetera, all are means of financial accountability.

Thus, the people deserve to be assured that the resources which they put at the disposal of government, its officials and agencies, are efficiently, effectively and economically managed and properly accounted for. However, the number and value of public sector activities have increased substantially in the public enterprises and the increase has led to the demand for financial accountability.

At the local government level, all categories of workers therein, need to render accounts of their activities to the public. The public in return, need to receive substantial accountability reports for proper assessment of their performance in the activities entrusted on them (the local government workers). According to Finer as quoted in Sharma and Sadana (2008), the best way to enforce financial accountability is to develop institutions that vigorously monitor the actions of public bureaucracy and punish those guilty of maladministration. This calls for various control measures to be put in places to ensure financial accountability in the local government bureaucracy.

Defining local government has not been easy (Abasili, Chioke & Udeoba, 2023), but in Nigeria, local government is a form of political and administrative decentralization established to extend governmental services to local levels, create a sense of belonging at the grassroots, and promote national integration and good governance (Ogunnubi, 2022). Aside this, there are certain features that constitute the essential features of an ideal local government. To this end, Chioke (2022) provided the following essential feature of an ideal local government:

Local government is any organized leadership/governance championed through the use of local personnel for the harnessing of material resources and human capital development at the grassroots level. Thus, the major focus of local government is the transformation

of material resources of local people and the development of human capital for participation in politics and contribution towards organizational goals as well as the overall sustainable national development (p.47).

Viewed from this angle, it is important to note that it is practically evident within our territorial jurisdiction that local government is not recognized as a federating unit. They are merely recognised in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as third tier. But are they really third tier government in all ramifications such as fiscal autonomy? They are not! If they are, then federalism is gone. It is apparent that there is no known provision for local government as a federating unit within Nigeria's democracy and other developed democracies of the globe and to think or talk of such is to engage in frivolity, absurdity, and vanity of the highest order. In a federal system, powers are shared between states and a central governing authority having postulated nationwide, sub-regional wide, regional wide or worldwide duties vested on it by the electorate through the instrumentality of the grundnorm, international conventions, and treaties (Chioke, 2021).

Therefore, the 1976 Local Government Reform Hand Book defines local government as: "Government at the local level exercised through representative councils established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas." Resonating the functional perspective of local government, Amoke (2020, p.193) pointed out that, "It is its responsibility to provide such services as portable water, rural electricity, health centres, roads networks, schools and their maintenance, etc. A local government that does these things is seen as an ideal local government providing service delivery."

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the structural-functional theory propounded by Almond (1966), Talcoth (1951) Levy (1951) Mitchel (1962). Structural functional theory views the society as a structure with interrelated parts designed to meet the biological and social needs of the individuals in the society (Chioke, 2022). The main concern was to develop a consistent and integrated theory from which can be derived from explanatory hypothesis relevant to all aspects of a political system.

Functionalism as a theory focuses on the functions performed in society by social structures such as institutions, hierarchies, and norms (Gómez-Diago, 2020). Structural functional theorists are of the view that says that society is made up of structures (Chioke, 2024).

Structural-functionalists all rest their theory on the premise of syllogism which Flamigan and Foreham, as cited in Orjiakor (2008) explained as follows:

That if a system "s" is to be maintained adequately under the prevailing conditions called "c" then requisite functions, $F_1F_2\text{---}F_n$, must be performed. And where the system "S" is being maintained adequately it can be reasonably inferred that the requisite functions, $F_1F_2\text{---}F_n$ are being performed, such function will be accomplished by existing structures.

In the field of political science, structures may be defined as the set of roles played by individuals and groups within an organization as a social system. These roles must, therefore, be seen in their interrelationship within the social system. Almond and Powel as cited in Orjiakor (2008) have referred to the term structure to mean the regularity with which "the activities which make up the political system are observed". They went on to illustrate this regular interaction of the observable activities with the setting of a court of law whose structure can be referred to as the interaction between the judge, the jury, the prosecuting and defense attorneys, witness, the defendant, and the plaintiff. From the theory, function is a set of roles played by individual in an organization. The structure of an organization determines how its function is to be performed.

The Relevance of the Theory to the Study

In applying this theory to the subject of this study, it is necessary to examine the role patterns of actors and the positions they occupy within the local government. Chairman is the chief executive and accounting officer of local government council. He is assisted by the supervisory councilors who are the political heads of their various departments. Local government workers are under them. By the virtue of employment contract of employees, statutory rules, societal norms and guidelines are put in place for workers to comply with. These employees are accountable for the work they are expected to do. The Local Government executive implements the policies and programmes of the council with help of the workers. The legislature makes bye-laws for the overall good of the council.

In every formal organization, there are procedural rules which are laid down for compliance by the public officers. These are internal and external measures for ensuring financial accountability. In implementing the policies and programmes of the council, Local Government officials have to adhere to the various control measures put in place to ensure financial accountability.

Accountability calls for human judgment as to whether assigned tasks have been satisfactorily discharged. Judgment in turn calls for authority: that is, the authority of one person to assess another's competence.

However, it is evident that local government was created to cater for the needs of the people at the grassroots. Any success or failure of the local government depends on how the local government officials comply with the various control measures put in place to ensure financial accountability in the system. But, the inability of the local government officials in Nigeria to discharge their statutory functions in compliance with the control measures has resulted to abysmal performance of the council.

Research Design

According to Nwana (1981), design is a term used to describe a number of decisions which need to be taken regarding the collection of data before ever data are collected. Thus, the design for this study involves the various steps, procedures and methods taken by the researcher in collecting and analyzing data for the study. In addition, this research work is a descriptive survey research which intends to examine public accountability in Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments of Enugu State. The term, population of the study refers to the total number of items or elements under observation in a particular research (Chioke, 2022). Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments have a population of one thousand two hundred (1200) workers. Also, the population of this study includes the six selected departments of Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments of Enugu State of Nigeria. The departments are finance, works, education, administration, health and agriculture. Three departments were selected from each of two local governments. Finance, education and works departments were selected from Udi Local Government for study while administration, health and agriculture were selected from Ezeagu Local Government for study. Twenty-three respondents were drawn from each of the selected departments of the two local governments. One hundred and thirty eight respondents were selected on the whole. Since the population has different and large segments or groups of people, the population was stratified or categorized on representative basis. They are presented as shown at the table below.

Stratified Population of the Respondents

Name of Departments	Number
Finance	300
Works	200
Education	200
Administration	200
Health	150
Agriculture	150
Total	1200

The departments are drawn from each of the two local governments. Additionally, in carrying out this study, the researcher elicited relevant data mainly through questionnaires that were administered to respondents in Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments of Enugu State. In order to get a representation of the whole population the Taro Yamani formula for sample size determination was used. The researcher administered one hundred and thirty eight (138) copies of questionnaire on the selected respondents of the six selected departments and one hundred and twenty were returned.

Data Analyses

Demographic Data of Respondents

The demographic data of the respondents are presented below, indicating their age, gender, education and occupational features.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-30 years	25	20.8
30-40 years	40	33.3
30-50 years	35	37.5
50yrs - above	10	8.4
Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The age distribution table shows that 20.8% of the respondents are between 20-30 years. While 33.3% of them fall between 30-40 years, and 37.5% of the respondents are between ages of 40-50 years. In addition, 8.4% of the respondents are between ages of 50-above. The implication of this distribution is that majority of the respondents are still within the working and productive age of 20-50 years. More importantly, the distribution also shows that most of the respondents

are still young and able-bodied people within the age bracket of 20-50 years. Thus, these people contribute meaningful to the socio-economic development of their local governments.

Table 2: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	85	70.8
Female	35	29.2
Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The gender distribution table as represented above shows that 70.8% of the respondents are males, while 29.2% of them are females. This explains that there are more male than female respondents in the research. Thus, the representation is gender sensitive enough and is gender sensitive comprehensive and thus is reliable for decision-making.

Table 3: Qualification of Respondents

Education	Frequency	Percentage(%)
FSLC	8	6.7
WASC/SSCE	20	16.7
OND/NCE	30	25
HND/B.Sc	50	41.6
M.Sc/PhD	12	10
Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The education distribution table above shows that 6.7% of the respondents completed their primary education while 16.7% of them possess secondary school certificate. Also, 25% of respondents either have OND or NCE, and 41.6% of them possess either HND or B.Sc. whereas 10% of them hold M.Sc/PhD. This representation underscores the fact that majority of the respondents are literate enough to give their view on the topic. Thus, they are educated enough to assess financial accountability in their various local governments.

Data on Variables of Subject of Investigation

Table 4: The Adherence of Local Government Officials to Internal Financial Control Measures

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1	Strongly agreed	4	3.3
2	Agreed	15	12.5
3	Undecided	3	2.5
4	Disagreed	38	31.7
5	Strongly disagreed	60	50
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Table 4 indicates that 3.3% of the respondents strongly agreed, 12.5% agreed, 2.5% undecided, 31.7% disagreed and 50% strongly disagreed. The implication of these responses is that greater percentage of respondent strongly disagreed that local government officials adhere strictly to the internal control measures.

Table 5: The Regularity of the Local Government Internal Auditing

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	4	3.4
2	Agreed	7	5.8
3	Undecided	10	8.3
4	Disagreed	29	24.2
5	Strongly disagreed	70	58.3
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 3.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 5.8% also agreed, 8.3% undecided, 24.2% disagreed and 58.3% strongly disagreed. This shows that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that local government conducts internal audit regularly.

Table 6: The local Government Adherence to Rules and Regulations Governing Financial Control

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	7	5.8
2	Agreed	10	8.3
3	Undecided	8	6.7
4	Disagreed	30	25
5	Strongly disagreed	65	54.2
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 5.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 8.3% also agreed, 6.7% were undecided, 25% disagreed and 54.2% strongly disagreed. This indicates that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that local government strictly adheres to rules and regulations governing financial control.

Table 7: The Existence of Adequate Safeguards for Custody of Funds and Other Resources of the Local Government.

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	11	9.2
2	Agreed	13	10.8
3	Undecided	10	8.3
4	Disagreed	36	30
5	Strongly disagreed	50	41.7
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the above table, 9.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 10.8% also agreed, 8.3% were undecided, 30% disagreed and 41.7% strongly disagreed. This shows that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that adequate safeguards exist for the custody of funds and other resources of the local government.

Table 8: The Submission of local Government Accounts and Records for checking and Reconciliation at the Prescribed Time

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	12	10
2	Agreed	10	8.3
3	Undecided		
4	Disagreed	50	41.7
5	Strongly disagreed	48	40
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The table above indicates that 10% of the respondents strongly agreed, 8.3% agreed, none was undecided, 41.7% disagreed and 40% strongly disagreed. This shows that greater percentage of respondents disagreed that accounts and records of the local government were submitted for checking and reconciliation at the prescribed time.

Table 9: Auditor General of Local Governments Monitoring of Financial Accountability in the Local Governments.

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	15	12.5
2	Agreed	10	8.3
3	Undecided	4	3.3
4	Disagreed	41	43.2
5	Strongly disagreed	50	41.7
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 12.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 8.3% also agreed, 3.3% were undecided, 34.2% disagreed and 41.7% also strongly disagreed. This indicates that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that the Auditor General of local governments monitors financial accountability in the local governments.

Table 10: The Performance of the Local Government Audit Alarm Committee in Financial Control

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	5	4.2
2	Agreed	7	5.8
3	Undecided	11	9.2
4	Disagreed	37	30.8
5	Strongly disagreed	60	50
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 4.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 5.8% agreed, 9.2% undecided, 30.8% disagreed and 50% strongly disagreed. This shows that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that the Local Government Audit Alarm Committee performs its functions in financial control.

Table 11: Comparative Statement of Payment and Receipts in the Financial Control of the Local Government

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	7	5.8
2	Agreed	13	10.8
3	Undecided	–	–
4	Disagreed	60	50
5	Strongly disagreed	40	33.4
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 5.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 10.8% agreed, none was undecided, 50% disagreed and 33.4% strongly disagreed. This indicates that greater percentage of the respondents disagreed that there is comparative statement of payment and receipts in the financial control of the local government.

Table 12: Good Records of Financial Transactions in the Local Government

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	8	6.7
2	Agreed	7	5.8
3	Undecided	3	2.5
4	Disagreed	25	20.8
5	Strongly disagreed	77	64.2
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 6.7% of respondents strongly agreed, 5.8% agreed, 2.5% undecided, 20.8% disagreed and 64.2% strongly disagreed. This shows that greater percentage of the respondents strongly disagreed that the local government keeps good records of financial transactions.

Table 13: Legislature and Oversight Function in Financial Control

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	15	12.5
2	Agreed	5	4.2
3	Undecided		
4	Disagreed	35	29.2
5	Strongly disagreed	65	54.1
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The table above shows that 12.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 4.2% agreed, none was undecided, 29.2% disagreed and 54.1% strongly disagreed. This indicates that greater percentage of respondents strongly disagreed that the legislature in the local government performs its oversight functions in financial control.

Table 14: The Satisfactory State of Financial Accountability in the Local Government Bureaucracies

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	12	10
2	Agreed	8	6.7
3	Undecided		
4	Disagreed	40	33.3
5	Strongly disagreed	60	50
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

From the table above, 10% of respondents strongly agreed, 6.7% agreed, none was undecided, 33.3% disagreed and 50% strongly disagreed. The implication of these responses is that greater percentage of respondents strongly disagreed that the state of financial accountability in the local government is satisfactory.

Table 15: Poor Financial Accountability Responsible for the Abysmal Performance of the Local Government

S/N	Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly agreed	63	52.5
2	Agreed	21	17.5
3	Undecided		
4	Disagreed	9	7.5
5	Strongly disagreed	27	22.5
	Total	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2011

The above table shows that 52.5% of the respondents strongly agreed, 17.5% agreed, none was undecided, 7.5% disagreed and 22.5% strongly disagreed. The above responses show that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that poor financial accountability is responsible for the abysmal performance of the local government. For instance a religious leader, Mr Agu Godwin attributed the poor performance of local government to unaccountability of the local government officials.

Test of Hypotheses

In order to test the hypotheses formulated for this study, a statistical tool known as chi-square (χ^2) was adopted to test the validity of the hypotheses.

Decision Rule

In the application of chi-square (χ^2) for the test of hypotheses, the following rule applied: reject the null hypothesis if the calculated value (cv) of the test statistic is greater than the table value (tv). Accept the null hypothesis if the calculate value (cv) of the test statistics is less than the table value (tv)

Hypothesis 1

Ho: There is no proper adherence to internal control measures in the two local governments

Ha: There is proper adherence to internal control measures in the two local governments

Critical value or table value 5.991

Thus, calculated value (0.1) is less than the critical value (5.991). Hence the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. It is therefore based on this that it is right to say that there is no proper adherence to internal control measures in the two local governments.

Hypothesis II

Ho: There is no effective system of external auditing in the financial control of the two local governments

Ha: There is effective system of external auditing in the financial control of the two local governments.

Critical value or table value = 5.991

Calculate Value = 0.33

Hence calculated value (0.33) is less than the critical value/table value (5.99), the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This shows that there is no effective system of external auditing in the financial control of the two local governments.

Hypothesis III

Ho: The two local governments do not follow proper authorization and recordings over revenue and expenditure.

Ha: The two local governments follow proper authorization and recordings over revenue and expenditure.

Critical value or table value = 5.991

Calculate Value = 4.01

Thus, calculated value (4.01) is less than the critical value/table value (5.99). For this reason, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This implies that Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments do not maintain adequate authorization and recordings to provide reasonable accounting controls over revenue and expenditure.

Hypothesis IV

Ho: There is no effective system of controls between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial accountability in the two local governments.

Ha: There is effective system of controls between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial accountability in the two local governments

Critical value or table value = 5.991

Calculate Value = 5.69

Hence calculated value (5.69) is less than the critical value/table value (5.99), the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This shows that there is no effective system of controls between the local government legislature and executive in ensuring financial accountability in the two local governments.

Discussion of Findings

Some of the important control measures are not religiously adhered to. Local government workers confirmed this. They also admit that audit committee is not effectively operational in the two local governments of Enugu State. The finding also showed that local government workers are afraid of the chief executives, that is, chairmen of the local governments. Even the internal auditors have this perception that if audit queries are issued and you force them to answer; it could lead to termination of their jobs or transfer to remote areas. This idea is true, because, there are many cases where internal auditors are victimized as a result of audit queries issued to chairmen. Internal auditors are employees of the local governments and are therefore, answerable to the chief executive.

The result of the interview was quite revealing and it corroborated the findings gathered through the questionnaire. There is lack of budgetary control in the two local governments. Sometimes, the chairmen can execute what is not in budget. In most cases, the disbursing officers do not comply with the rules of the budget and this hinders financial accountability. The council budgets are usually not presented to the council prior to the state government approval. Money is often paid for the contracts that are awarded without execution. Nobody monitors the implementations of what is in budget. Responses during interview with workers of Udi and Ezeagu Local governments of Enugu State indicate "everything is shrouded in mystery".

Moreover, employees of local governments are of the view that mails are not handled by those who are responsible for the auditing records, accounting records not maintained and shown regularly to members before audit exercise. This often may result in a situation whereby workers in the accounting sections connive with the chief executive to misappropriate local government resources. This complies with Nwoko's (1993) assertion that workers in accounting in accounting department, due to longevity in particular office, connive with the chief executives to embezzle local government resources.

During the interview session, the research observed that the members of the local government executive meet when they are resources to share contrary to the rules in the local government law. These members of the local government shun some of their responsibilities and direct their attention to the one that will benefit them. Workers in these local governments follow the footsteps of the members of the local government executives by not coming to work always.

There are no checks and balances between the executive and the legislature. Money can be withdrawn and spent by the executive without the knowledge of the legislature.

Local government workers interviewed, confessed that there is nothing like effective accountability in the two local governments. Majority of the respondents are of the view that most of these measures installed in the system are just there without any practical recognition and application. This has practical implication. It suggests that if these important measures are not adhered to, there is every likelihood that poor financial accountability in Nigeria local government bureaucracies could lead to crippling of local government activities. The overall consequences have been the running down of the economy of the local government and the attendant hardship for the people at the grassroots. According to Scott (1998), the situation put the economy of the grassroots to jeopardy. It is evident; therefore, that there is need for strict adherence of these measures so as to reduce unaccountability in the Nigeria local government.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the results of the study generally show that all the control measures installed in Udi and Ezeagu Local Governments are not adhered to. The results imply that the local government functionaries in Udi and Ezeagu local government do not adhere to the principles of financial accountability in the conduct of the affairs of the council. Hence, there is prevalence of poor accountability in local government bureaucracies.

Based on the findings of this research, the researcher recommended that:

Career and elected officials should insist on the application of the control mechanism while discharging their duties.

The audit units of each local government should be well established and strengthened with sufficient paraphernalia of office, adequate personnel and space.

The Auditor General of local governments should effectively monitor financial accountability in the local governments.

All the revenues and expenditures of the local government should be properly authorized and recorded to avoid any fraudulent practice.

There must be a system of checks and balances between the executive and legislature in the local governments.

References

- Abasili, N. K., Chioke, S.C. & Udeoba, C.E. (2023). Assessing the need for manpower development in local government in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*. 29: 18-30 <https://doi.org/10.47743/jopafnl-2023-29-02>
- Abdusalami, A. (1999), *Accountability and Policy Making in the Local Government System* in I. N. Obasi & N. O. Yagub (eds) *Local Government Policy Making and Executive in Nigeria*, Ibadan: Sam Bookman Publishers.
- Amoke, E. I. (2020). Towards an ideal local governments in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance Research*. 3(1), 191 – 204
- Chioke, S.C (2024). Can lamb and lion tango? Investigating Nigeria's practice of public administration and peculiar challenges from structural functional theory. *PanAfrican Journal of Governance and Development*. 5(1)
- Chioke, S.C. (2023). Responsible leadership and accountability challenge in Nigeria's public administration and sustainable development: A glocalised perspective. *Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Science*, 16, 98-116 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7605676>
- Chioke, S. C. (2022). Ontology of Nigerian local governments: A functional approach towards the global pattern. *Extensive Reviews*, 2(1); 45 – 55 <https://doi.org/10.21467/exr.2.1.4710>
- Chioke, S. C. (2021). Anatomy of Nigerian federalism: A reflection of the nagging challenges and prospects from a cultural relativist perspective. *PanAfrican Journal of Governance and Development*. 2(2), 232 – 256 <https://doi.org/10.46404/panjogov.v2i2.3237>
- Chioke, S. C. (2017). An overview of bureaucracy and treasury single account in an era of economic change. *Journal of Research in Science and Technology Education*. 7(2). 1 – 13
- Chioke, S. C. (2016). *The impact of treasury single account on the administration of State and National Bureaucracy: A study of Nigerian Immigration Service, Enugu State Command*. M.Sc. Thesis submitted to the Department of Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria.
- Chioke, S. C. (2012). *First step on the study of public administration*. Enugu: Prince Digital Press
- Chioke, S. C., Umeokafor, C. C & Mbamalu, K. U. (2020). Local government autonomy and rural development: Imperative issues and challenges bedeviling local governments in Southeast geopolitical zone, Nigeria. *International Journal of Current*

- Research 12(12), 15154 –15161
<https://doi.org/10.24941/ijcr.40322.12.2020>
- Coe, C.K., Ellis, C. (1994), *Internal Control in State, Local and non-profit Agencies*, London: John Wiley and Sons.
- Duncan, B. J., Flesher, D. L. & Stocks, M. H (1999). An Examination of the Effects of Church Size and Denomination on Systems of Internal Controls. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Accountability* 2(2).
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1976). *Local Government Reform Guidelines*. Lagos: Government Printers.
- Gómez-Diago G. (2020). Functionalist theory. In Merskin, D. L. (ed.). *The SAGE international encyclopedia of mass media and society*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications Inc.
- Hornby A. S (ed.) (2010). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (7th ed.) New York: Oxford University Press
- Laxmikanth, M. (2006). *Public Administration for the UPSC Civil Services Preliminary Examination*, New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd.
- Nwana (1981). *Introduction to education Research*. Ibadan: Heinemann.
- Nwoko, C. (1993). *Effective Internal Controls in Organisations*. Enugu: Academic Publishers
- Orjiakor, C.C. (2008), *Revenue Mobilization and Public Accountability in the Local Government in Enugu State*. A Project submitted to the Department of Public Administration and Local Government, Faculty of Social Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Scott, W.R. (1998). *Institutions and Theory of Organization*, London: Heinemann Publishers.
- Ugwu, E. & Okonkwo, B. S. (2015). *Administrative Theories and Practice*. Enugu: Don-Ell Printing & Pub. Co.